

A NOTE ON A CONJECTURE OF ERDŐS-TURÁN

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Abstract

Let $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a strictly increasing sequence of nonnegative integers. We prove that for $F(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^{a_n}$ and $F(x)^2 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} R(n)x^n$, the condition $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) = A$ for some positive integer A implies that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) \leq A - 2\sqrt{A} + 1$.

1. Introduction

Suppose that $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is a strictly increasing sequence of nonnegative integers. Let

$$F(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^{a_n}$$

and

$$F(x)^2 = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} R(n)x^n.$$

The sequence $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is called an *additive basis of order two* if $R(n) > 0$ for every nonnegative integer n and an *asymptotic additive basis of order two* if $R(n) > 0$ for every sufficiently large n . The Erdős-Turán conjecture says that for any additive basis of order two $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ the sequence $\{R(n)\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ is unbounded. This conjecture can be rephrased in number theoretic language: Let $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a strictly increasing sequence of integers. Denote by $R(n)$ the number of solution $n = a_i + a_j$, i.e.,

$$R(n) = \#\{(i, j) : n = a_i + a_j\}.$$

Using this representation function the Erdős-Turán conjecture can be stated as follows,

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Conjecture 1 (Erdős-Turán conjecture for bases of order two) *Let $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ be a strictly increasing sequence of nonnegative integers such that $R(n) > 0$ for every nonnegative integer n . Then the sequence $\{R(n)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is unbounded.*

Grekos, Haddad, Helou and Pihko [3] proved that $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) \geq 6$ for every basis $\{a_n\}$. Later Borwein, Choi and Chu [1] improved it to $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) \geq 8$.

If for some strictly increasing sequence nonnegative integers $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ the representation function $R(n) > 0$ for every $n \geq n_0$ (that is $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ forms an asymptotic additive basis), then the sequence $\{0, 1, \dots, n_0 - 1\} \cup \{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ forms a basis and if its representation function is denoted by $R'(n)$ then $R'(n) \leq R(n) + n_0$. Therefore, we get that the above conjecture is equivalent to

Conjecture 2 (Erdős-Turán conjecture for asymptotic bases of order 2) *Suppose that $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is a strictly increasing sequence of nonnegative integers such that $R(n) > 0$ for every $n \geq n_0$. Then the sequence $\{R(n)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is unbounded.*

This second version can be formulated as:

Conjecture 3 (Erdős-Turán conjecture for bounded representation function) *Suppose that $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is a strictly increasing sequence of nonnegative integers and*

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) = A$$

for some positive integer A . Then we have $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) = 0$.

In this note we give a non-trivial upper bound for $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n)$ if the sequence $\{R(n)\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is bounded.

Theorem 1 *Suppose that $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is a strictly increasing sequence of nonnegative integers and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) = A$ for some positive integer A . Then we have*

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) \leq A - 2\sqrt{A} + 1.$$

2. Proof

If $a_N > N^2$ for some N , then

$$\#\{n : 1 \leq n \leq N^2, R(n) > 0\} \leq \binom{N}{2},$$

and therefore

$$\#\{n : 1 \leq n \leq N^2, R(n) = 0\} \geq \binom{N+1}{2}.$$

Hence it follows that if $a_n > n^2$ for infinitely many integers n , then $R(n) = 0$ for infinitely many integers n . Then we have $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) = 0 \leq A - 2\sqrt{A} + 1$, which proves the theorem.

Therefore we may assume that

$$a_n \leq n^2 \quad \text{for } n \geq n_1. \tag{1}$$

Let us suppose that there exists a strictly increasing sequence of nonnegative integers $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ such that $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) = A$ but $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} R(n) > A - 2\sqrt{A} + 1$. Then there exist an integer n_2 and $0 < \epsilon < \sqrt{A}$ for which $A - 2\sqrt{A} + 1 + \epsilon \leq R(n) \leq A$ for $n \geq n_2$. Set $C = A - \sqrt{A} + \epsilon$. By elementary calculus we have $f(x) = \frac{(x-C)^2}{x} < 1$ for every $x \in [A - 2\sqrt{A} + 1 + \epsilon, A]$, and therefore there exists a $\delta > 0$ such that

$$(R(n) - C)^2 \leq (1 - \delta)^2 R(n) \quad \text{for } n \geq n_2. \tag{2}$$

Let

$$F(z) = \sum_{n=1}^\infty z^{a_n}.$$

Then

$$F(z)^2 = \sum_{n=0}^\infty R(n)z^n.$$

Let

$$z = \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right)e^{2\pi i\alpha} = re^{2\pi i\alpha},$$

where N is a large integer. We give an upper and a lower bound for the integral

$$\int_0^1 |F(z)^2 - \sum_{n=0}^\infty Cz^n| d\alpha \tag{3}$$

to reach a contradiction. We get an upper bound for (3) by Cauchy's inequality, Parseval's formula and (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 |F(z)^2 - \sum_{n=0}^\infty Cz^n| d\alpha &= \int_0^1 \left| \sum_{n=0}^\infty (R(n) - C)z^n \right| d\alpha \leq \left(\int_0^1 \left| \sum_{n=0}^\infty (R(n) - C)z^n \right|^2 d\alpha \right)^{1/2} = \\ &= \left(\sum_{n=0}^\infty (R(n) - C)^2 r^{2n} \right)^{1/2} \leq \left(c_1 + (1 - \delta)^2 \left(\sum_{n=0}^\infty R(n)r^{2n} \right) \right)^{1/2} \leq c_2 + (1 - \delta)F(r^2). \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Now here is the lower bound for (3). Obviously,

$$\int_0^1 |F(z)^2 - \sum_{n=0}^\infty Cz^n| d\alpha \geq \int_0^1 |F(z)^2| d\alpha - \int_0^1 \left| \sum_{n=0}^\infty Cz^n \right| d\alpha, \tag{5}$$

where by Parseval's formula

$$\int_0^1 |F^2(z)|d\alpha = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{2a_n} = F(r^2). \tag{6}$$

Moreover

$$\int_0^1 \left| \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Cz^n \right| d\alpha = C \int_0^1 \frac{1}{|1-z|} d\alpha = 2C \int_0^{1/2} \frac{1}{|1-z|} d\alpha.$$

Since

$$|1-z|^2 = (1-r \cos 2\pi\alpha)^2 + (r \sin 2\pi\alpha)^2 = (1-r)^2 + 2r(1-\cos 2\pi\alpha) = (1-r)^2 + 4r \sin^2 \pi\alpha,$$

we have $|1-z| \geq \max\{\frac{1}{N}, \alpha\}$ for every $0 < \alpha < \frac{1}{2}$. Hence

$$\int_0^1 \left| \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Cz^n \right| d\alpha \leq 2C \left(\int_0^{1/N} N d\alpha \right) + \int_{1/N}^{1/2} \frac{1}{\alpha} d\alpha \leq c_3 \log N \tag{7}$$

for some $c_3 > 0$. By (4), (6) and (7) we have

$$F(r^2) - c_3 \log N \leq \int_0^1 |F^2(z) - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Cz^n| d\alpha \leq (1-\delta)F(r^2) + c_2;$$

therefore

$$\delta F(r^2) < c_2 + c_3 \log N, \tag{8}$$

but in view of (1)

$$F(r^2) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} r^{2a_n} \geq \sum_{n=n_1}^{\sqrt{N}} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right)^{2a_n} > c_4 \sqrt{N}$$

for some positive c_4 , which is a contradiction to (8) if N is large enough. □

References

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